

Improved Stability Criteria for Neural Networks with Two Additive Time-Varying Delays

Authors : Miaomiao~Yang, Shouming~Zhong

Abstract : This paper studies the problem of stability criteria for neural networks with two additive time-varying delays. A new Lyapunov function is constructed and some new delay-dependent stability criteria are derived in terms of linear matrix inequalities (LMI), zero equalities and reciprocally convex approach. The several stability criterion proposed in this paper is simpler and effective. Finally, numerical examples are provided to demonstrate the feasibility and effectiveness of our results.

Keywords : Stability, Neural networks, Linear Matrix Inequalities (LMI), Lyapunov function, Time-varying delays.

Conference Title : ICEP 2014 : International Conference on Electronic Publications

Conference Location : journal city, WASET

Conference Dates : November 23-23, 2014